

Results of the survey of the ZKI working group Strategy and Organization on software solutions at universities 2021

Malte Dreyer, Humboldt University Berlin, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1775-8622>

malte.dreyer@hu-berlin.de

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Introduction

At present, the ZKI does not yet have an overview of which software solutions are used how frequently at the member institutions. The aim of this survey is therefore to gain a better picture of the solutions in use and to create a helpful means of comparison for many institutions by querying particularly central systems.

The survey was answered by 89 universities. Up to 83 responses were given for the individual categories of software solutions. Participation in the survey was possible from 20.4.2021 to 21.5.2021.

The survey asked about the following categories:

- Backup Software
- Campus Management Systems - CaMS
- Content Management Systems - CMS
- Chat / Instant Messaging Solutions - IM
- Document Management Systems - DMS
- Research Information System - FIS
- Calendar
- Learning Management Systems - LMS
- Mail
- Private Cloud / VM Management
- Project Management Software
- Resource Management Systems
- Sync-n-Share solutions
- Ticket / Incident Management Systems
- Video management systems
- Video conferencing solutions
- Knowledge Management Solutions

For each category, the following questions were asked:

- Which solution do you use?
- Is the system commercial, open source, homegrown, or hybrid?
- How do you operate the system? Internally, externally or mixed?
- How satisfied are you with the solution? (Scale from 1 - very dissatisfied to 10 - very satisfied)
- What comments do you have?

In addition, the survey asked about type of institution of higher education, state, and number of students at the institution.

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Summary

The data for the individual categories varies widely. Some categories are significantly characterized by open source solutions, while other categories are almost exclusively represented by commercial solutions. Clear differences can be identified between larger and smaller institutions. Smaller institutions show greater diversity in the solutions used across all categories. Similar, but not quite as pronounced, are corresponding differences between universities and universities of applied sciences. The diversity of solutions at HAWs is slightly higher.

The following chart shows the top solutions for each category - open source solutions are marked in green and commercial solutions in blue.

Category	Place 1	Quantity	Place 2	Quantity	Place 3	Quantity
Backup	Veeam	23	IBM Spectrum Protect	21	Dell EMC Networker	5
Campus Management System	HISinOne	41	HIS GX	21	CampusNet	8
Content Management System	Typo3	45	Plone	6	Imperia	5
Document Management System	Codia d.3	27	Lib-IT Filero	4	ELO Digital Office	3
Research Information System	HIS	10	HISinOne-RES	7	Clarivate Converis	4
Incident Management	OTRS	30	KIX Professional	7	Zammad	6
Instant messaging	Microsoft Teams	12	RocketChat	11	Matrix	8
Calendar	Microsoft Exchange	52	SOGO	5	Microfocus Groupwise	4
Learning management system	Moodle	37	Ilias	13	Stud.IP	9
Mail	Microsoft Exchange	50	Dovecot	9	GroupWise	2
Project Management	GitLab	24	Jira	7	OpenProject	6
Resource Management	SAP	21	HIS	20	Make	9
Sync-n-Share	NextCloud	33	OwnCloud	12	PowerFolder	11
Video conferencing	BigBlueButton	31	Zoom	29	Cisco WebEx	9
Video Management	OpenCast	25	Panopto	10	Vimp	7
Private Cloud / VM Management	VMWare	55	Proxmox	4	Microsoft Hyper-V	3
Knowledge Management	Confluence	16	Microsoft SharePoint	12	Mediawiki	9

Details of the participating facilities

Comprehensive evaluations

The license types are distributed across all categories as follows:

For operating models, the distribution across all categories is as follows:

By type of university, the distribution of license types across all categories is as follows:

Across all categories, license types by number of students are distributed as follows:

The following chart shows the distribution of operating modes across all categories by type of university:

The distribution of operating modes across all categories by number of students is shown in the following chart:

Backup

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen
Bis zu 5.000	22
Backup Exec	1
Bacula	1
Bareos	1
Dell EMC-Networker	2
IBM Spectrum Protect	6
NetApp Snapshots, tar	1
Veeam	9
Veritas NetBackup	1
5.001 bis 15.000	25
Bacula	1
Bareos	1
CommVault	1
Comvault Simpana	1
Dell EMC-Networker	3
HP Data Protector	2
IBM Spectrum Protect	3
Quest NetVault	1
rsync	1
Veeam	10
VMWare	1
15.001 bis 30.000	11
Bacula	1
IBM Spectrum Protect	7
Olbackup	1
Veeam	2
Mehr als 30.000	10
Atempo	2
Bacula	1
IBM Spectrum Protect	5
Veeam	2
Gesamtergebnis	68

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
▣ Duale Hochschule	1
Veeam	1
▣ Forschungseinrichtung	1
IBM Spectrum Protect	1
▣ Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	32
Backup Exec	1
Bacula	2
Bareos	1
Comvault Simpana	1
Dell EMC-Networker	3
HP Data Protector	2
IBM Spectrum Protect	4
Veeam	16
Veritas NetBackup	1
VMWare	1
▣ Kunst- / Musik-Hochschule	1
Bareos	1
▣ Sonstiges	1
NetApp Snapshots, tar	1
▣ Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule	1
Veeam	1
▣ Universität	31
Atempo	2
Bacula	2
CommVault	1
Dell EMC-Networker	2
IBM Spectrum Protect	16
Olbackup	1
Quest NetVault	1
rsync	1
Veeam	5
Gesamtergebnis	68

CaMS - Campus Management System

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen	
Bis zu 5.000		26
CampusNet		2
CampusNet Classic		2
CAS Campus		1
HIS GX		6
HISinOne		12
PRIMUSS		2
selbst entwickelte Lösung		1
5.001 bis 15.000		31
Academy Five		2
CampusNet		3
HIS GX		7
HISinOne		18
OpenCampus		1
15.001 bis 30.000		13
CampusNet		2
HIS GX		3
HISinOne		8
Mehr als 30.000		11
CampusNet		1
CampusOnline		1
HIS GX		5
HISinOne		3
SAP SLCM		1
Gesamtergebnis		81

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen	
Duale Hochschule		1
CampusNet		1
Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften		42
Academy Five		2
CampusNet		3
CampusNet Classic		2
HIS GX		9
HISinOne		24
PRIMUSS		2
Kunst- / Musik-Hochschule		1
HISinOne		1
Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule		3
CampusNet		1
CAS Campus		1
selbst entwickelte Lösung		1
Universität		34
CampusNet		3
CampusOnline		1
HIS GX		12
HISinOne		16
OpenCampus		1
SAP SLCM		1
Gesamtergebnis		81

Chat / Instant Messaging

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen
Bis zu 5.000	15
Matrix	2
Mattermost	2
Microsoft Teams	6
RocketChat	4
WebexTeams	1
5.001 bis 15.000	20
Cisco Jabber	1
Cisco Webex	2
Just Connect	1
Matrix	3
Mattermost	1
Microsoft Teams	5
RocketChat	5
Skype for Business	1
WebexTeams	1
15.001 bis 30.000	9
Cisco Jabber	1
Jabber	2
Matrix	1
Mattermost	2
Rainbow	1
RocketChat	1
Zoom	1
Mehr als 30.000	7
Cisco Webex	1
Matrix	2
Mattermost	1
Microsoft Teams	1
RocketChat	1
Zulip	1
Gesamtergebnis	51

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
Forschungseinrichtung	1
Mattermost	1
Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	25
Cisco Jabber	2
Cisco Webex	2
Just Connect	1
Matrix	4
Mattermost	1
Microsoft Teams	8
RocketChat	4
Skype for Business	1
WebexTeams	2
Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule	1
Microsoft Teams	1
Universität	24
Cisco Webex	1
Jabber	2
Matrix	4
Mattermost	4
Microsoft Teams	3
Rainbow	1
RocketChat	7
Zoom	1
Zulip	1
Gesamtergebnis	51

CMS - Content Management System

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen	
Bis zu 5.000		24
Cabacos		2
Drupal		2
Government Site Builder		1
Plone		1
synfo		1
Typo3		16
Wordpress		1
5.001 bis 15.000		28
CMS Fiona		1
Drupal		1
Imperia		2
OpenCMS		1
SharePoint		1
TUCAL		1
Typo3		21
15.001 bis 30.000		12
DjangoCMS		1
EgoCMS		1
FirstSpirit		1
Imperia		1
Plone		3
Typo3		5
Mehr als 30.000		10
Imperia		2
Plone		2
Typo3		3
Wordpress		3
Gesamtergebnis		74

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp		Nennungen
▣ Duale Hochschule		1
Typo3		1
▣ Forschungseinrichtung		1
Plone		1
▣ Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften		38
Cabacos		2
Drupal		2
Imperia		3
OpenCMS		1
SharePoint		1
Typo3		28
Wordpress		1
▣ Kunst- / Musik-Hochschule		1
synfo		1
▣ Sonstiges		1
Government Site Builder		1
▣ Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule		1
Typo3		1
▣ Universität		31
CMS Fiona		1
DjangoCMS		1
Drupal		1
EgoCMS		1
FirstSpirit		1
Imperia		2
Plone		5
TUCAL		1
Typo3		15
Wordpress		3
Gesamtergebnis		74

DMS - Document Management System

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen
Bis zu 5.000	11
Alfresco	1
Codia d.3	8
Fabersoft eAkte Bund	1
Lib-IT Filero	1
5.001 bis 15.000	20
Alfresco	2
Codia d.3	11
ELO Digital Office	2
Formcycle	1
Intrexx QMS	1
Lib-IT Filero	2
SharePoint	1
15.001 bis 30.000	6
Codia d.3	4
Doxis4	2
Mehr als 30.000	7
Codia d.3	4
ELO Digital Office	1
Lib-IT Filero	1
SAP Foldersmanagement	1
Gesamtergebnis	44

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
Duale Hochschule	1
Lib-IT Filero	1
Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	24
Alfresco	3
Codia d.3	16
ELO Digital Office	1
Intrexx QMS	1
Lib-IT Filero	3
Sonstiges	1
Fabersoft eAkte Bund	1
Universität	18
Codia d.3	11
Doxis4	2
ELO Digital Office	2
Formcycle	1
SAP Foldersmanagement	1
SharePoint	1
Gesamtergebnis	44

FIS - Research Information System

The nominations are ¹:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

¹ The distinction between HIS and HISinOneRES corresponds to the answers given. It is not clear from the responses whether both answers refer to the same product.

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen
Bis zu 5.000	9
Eigenentwicklung	2
Elsevier Pur	1
Forschungsdatenbank	1
HIS	2
HISinOne-RES	2
Proveda	1
5.001 bis 15.000	17
DSpaceCRIS	1
Eigenentwicklung	5
HIS	4
HISinOne-RES	4
HIS-LSF	2
Universis	1
15.001 bis 30.000	6
Clarivate Converis	1
Elsevier Pur	1
FactScience	1
HIS	3
Mehr als 30.000	6
Clarivate Converis	3
Elsevier Pur	1
HIS	1
HISinOne-RES	1
Gesamtergebnis	38

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	17
Eigenentwicklung	6
HIS	5
HISinOne-RES	4
Proveda	1
Universis	1
Universität	21
Clarivate Converis	4
DSpaceCRIS	1
Eigenentwicklung	1
Elsevier Pur	3
FactScience	1
Forschungsdatenbank	1
HIS	5
HISinOne-RES	3
HIS-LSF	2
Gesamtergebnis	38

Calendar

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen	
Bis zu 5.000		24
Davical		1
GroupOffice		1
Horde		1
Microfocus Groupwise		3
Microsoft Exchange		16
Nextcloud Calendar		1
Zimbra Kalender		1
5.001 bis 15.000		27
Microsoft Exchange		22
open Xchange		1
Oracle Beehive		1
SOGo		1
Tine		2
15.001 bis 30.000		12
Bedework		1
Microfocus Groupwise		1
Microsoft Exchange		8
SOGo		2
Mehr als 30.000		9
CommuniGate Pro		1
Microsoft Exchange		6
SOGo		2
Gesamtergebnis		72

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
▣ Duale Hochschule	1
Microsoft Exchange	1
▣ Forschungseinrichtung	1
Nextcloud Calendar	1
▣ Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	37
GroupOffice	1
Microfocus Groupwise	4
Microsoft Exchange	27
open Xchange	1
Oracle Beehive	1
Tine	2
Zimbra Kalender	1
▣ Kunst- / Musik-Hochschule	1
Davical	1
▣ Sonstiges	1
Microsoft Exchange	1
▣ Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule	1
Microsoft Exchange	1
▣ Universität	30
Bedework	1
CommuniGate Pro	1
Horde	1
Microsoft Exchange	22
SOG	5
Gesamtergebnis	72

LMS - Learning Management System

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen	
Bis zu 5.000		23
Ilias		2
Moodle		13
OPAL		3
Open OLAT		2
Sharepoint Portal+		1
Stud.IP		2
5.001 bis 15.000		27
CampusNet		1
Ilias		7
Moodle		13
OPAL		2
Stud.IP		3
TraiNex		1
15.001 bis 30.000		12
Ilias		1
Moodle		6
OLAT		1
Open OLAT		1
Stud.IP		3
Mehr als 30.000		9
Ilias		3
Moodle		5
Stud.IP		1
Gesamtergebnis		71

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
▣ Duale Hochschule	1
Moodle	1
▣ Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	37
CampusNet	1
Ilias	7
Moodle	20
OPAL	2
Open OLAT	2
Sharepoint Portal+	1
Stud.IP	4
▣ Kunst- / Musik-Hochschule	1
OPAL	1
▣ Sonstiges	1
Ilias	1
▣ Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule	1
Moodle	1
▣ Universität	30
Ilias	5
Moodle	15
OLAT	1
OPAL	2
Open OLAT	1
Stud.IP	5
TraiNex	1
Gesamtergebnis	71

Mail

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen	
Bis zu 5.000		24
Courier		1
Dovecot		2
GroupOffice		1
GroupWise		2
Horde		1
Microsoft Exchange		16
Zimbra		1
5.001 bis 15.000		26
Dovecot		3
exim		1
Microsoft Exchange		20
Oracle Beehive		1
postfix		1
15.001 bis 30.000		12
Cyrus		1
Dovecot		1
Micro Focus GroupWise		1
Microsoft Exchange		9
Mehr als 30.000		9
CommuniGate Pro		1
Dovecot		3
Microsoft Exchange		5
Gesamtergebnis		71

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
▣ Duale Hochschule	1
Microsoft Exchange	1
▣ Forschungseinrichtung	1
Courier	1
▣ Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	36
Dovecot	2
GroupOffice	1
GroupWise	2
Micro Focus GroupWise	1
Microsoft Exchange	27
Oracle Beehive	1
postfix	1
Zimbra	1
▣ Kunst- / Musik-Hochschule	1
Dovecot	1
▣ Sonstiges	1
Microsoft Exchange	1
▣ Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule	1
Microsoft Exchange	1
▣ Universität	30
CommuniGate Pro	1
Cyrus	1
Dovecot	6
exim	1
Horde	1
Microsoft Exchange	20
Gesamtergebnis	71

Private Cloud / VM Management

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen	
Bis zu 5.000		19
Microsoft Hyper-V		1
Nextcloud		1
Nutanix		1
VMWare		16
5.001 bis 15.000		26
Microsoft Hyper-V		2
Oracle VM		1
Proxmox		2
VMWare		21
15.001 bis 30.000		12
Proxmox		1
VMWare		11
Mehr als 30.000		10
OpenStack		1
oVirt		1
Proxmox		1
VMWare		7
Gesamtergebnis		67

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen	
Duale Hochschule		1
VMWare		1
Forschungseinrichtung		1
Nutanix		1
Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften		32
Microsoft Hyper-V		2
Oracle VM		1
Proxmox		1
VMWare		28
Kunst- / Musik-Hochschule		1
VMWare		1
Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule		1
Microsoft Hyper-V		1
Universität		31
Nextcloud		1
OpenStack		1
oVirt		1
Proxmox		3
VMWare		25
Gesamtergebnis		67

Project Management

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen
Bis zu 5.000	12
GitHub	1
GitLab	5
Microsoft Project	2
Microsoft Teams	1
OpenProject	2
Redmine	1
5.001 bis 15.000	20
GitLab	10
Jira	4
Microsoft Project	2
OpenProject	2
Redmine	1
Trello	1
15.001 bis 30.000	10
GitLab	7
Jira	1
Jira ServiceDesk	1
Redmine	1
Mehr als 30.000	8
GitLab	2
Jira	2
OnlyOffice	1
OpenProject	2
Sharepoint	1
Gesamtergebnis	50

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp		Nennungen
▣ Duale Hochschule		1
OpenProject		1
▣ Forschungseinrichtung		1
GitLab		1
▣ Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften		25
GitLab		11
Jira		5
Microsoft Project		2
Microsoft Teams		1
OpenProject		4
Redmine		1
Trello		1
▣ Sonstiges		1
Microsoft Project		1
▣ Universität		22
GitHub		1
GitLab		12
Jira		2
Jira ServiceDesk		1
Microsoft Project		1
OnlyOffice		1
OpenProject		1
Redmine		2
Sharepoint		1
Gesamtergebnis		50

Resource Management

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen	
Bis zu 5.000		16
HIS		8
Mach		4
PRIMUS RS		1
SAP		3
5.001 bis 15.000		17
HIS		7
Mach		3
SAP		7
15.001 bis 30.000		10
HIS		3
Mach		2
SAP		5
Mehr als 30.000		9
HIS		2
RAPLA		1
SAP		6
Gesamtergebnis		52

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen	
Duale Hochschule		1
RAPLA		1
Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften		24
HIS		10
Mach		6
PRIMUS RS		1
SAP		7
Kunst- / Musik-Hochschule		1
HIS		1
Universität		26
HIS		9
Mach		3
SAP		14
Gesamtergebnis		52

Sync-n-Share

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen
Bis zu 5.000	23
Micro Focus Filr	2
NextCloud	12
OwnCloud	2
PowerFolder	3
Seafile	3
Teamdrive	1
5.001 bis 15.000	26
Micro Focus Filr	1
Microsoft OneDrive	2
NextCloud	13
OwnCloud	5
PowerFolder	3
Seafile	2
15.001 bis 30.000	12
NextCloud	6
OwnCloud	2
PowerFolder	3
Teamdrive	1
Mehr als 30.000	9
NextCloud	2
OwnCloud	3
PowerFolder	2
Seafile	2
Gesamtergebnis	70

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
Duale Hochschule	1
NextCloud	1
Forschungseinrichtung	1
NextCloud	1
Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	36
Micro Focus Filr	3
Microsoft OneDrive	1
NextCloud	15
OwnCloud	6
PowerFolder	5
Seafile	5
Teamdrive	1
Kunst- / Musik-Hochschule	1
NextCloud	1
Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule	1
NextCloud	1
Universität	30
Microsoft OneDrive	1
NextCloud	14
OwnCloud	6
PowerFolder	6
Seafile	2
Teamdrive	1
Gesamtergebnis	70

Ticket / Incident Management

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen
Bis zu 5.000	21
AixBoms	1
Echolon	1
GPLI	1
GroupOffice	1
KIX Professional	2
Matrix42	2
OK-Ticket	1
OTRS	7
Zammad	4
Znuny (OTRS)	1
5.001 bis 15.000	24
JIRA	2
Jira Service Desk	1
KIX Professional	2
Microfocus SMAX	1
osTicket	2
OTOBO	1
OTRS	10
Topdesk	1
Zammad	2
Znuny (OTRS)	2
15.001 bis 30.000	12
Eigenentwicklung	1
Jira Service Desk	1
KIX Professional	1
OTRS	8
Topdesk	1
Mehr als 30.000	9
KIX Professional	2
OTRS	5
TicketXpert	1
Znuny (OTRS)	1
Gesamtergebnis	66

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp		Nennungen
▣ Duale Hochschule		1
OTRS		1
▣ Forschungseinrichtung		1
OTRS		1
▣ Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften		33
Eigenentwicklung		1
GPLI		1
GroupOffice		1
JIRA		2
Jira Service Desk		1
KIX Professional		4
Microfocus SMAX		1
OK-Ticket		1
osTicket		1
OTOBO		1
OTRS		10
Topdesk		2
Zammad		5
Znuny (OTRS)		2
▣ Sonstiges		1
AixBoms		1
▣ Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule		1
OTRS		1
▣ Universität		29
Echolon		1
Jira Service Desk		1
KIX Professional		3
Matrix42		2
osTicket		1
OTRS		17
TicketXpert		1
Zammad		1
Znuny (OTRS)		2
Gesamtergebnis		66

Video conferencing

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen
Bis zu 5.000	25
BigBlueButton	11
Cisco WebEx	3
Microsoft Teams	5
Zoom	6
5.001 bis 15.000	27
Adobe Connect	1
BigBlueButton	12
Cisco WebEx	2
Microsoft Teams	3
Zoom	9
15.001 bis 30.000	14
BigBlueButton	4
Cisco WebEx	2
Zoom	8
Mehr als 30.000	13
BigBlueButton	4
Cisco WebEx	2
Jitsi	1
Zoom	6
Gesamtergebnis	79

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
Duale Hochschule	1
BigBlueButton	1
Forschungseinrichtung	1
Zoom	1
Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	38
BigBlueButton	17
Cisco WebEx	3
Microsoft Teams	7
Zoom	11
Kunst- / Musik-Hochschule	1
Cisco WebEx	1
Sonstiges	1
Cisco WebEx	1
Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule	1
Zoom	1
Universität	36
Adobe Connect	1
BigBlueButton	13
Cisco WebEx	4
Jitsi	1
Microsoft Teams	1
Zoom	16
Gesamtergebnis	79

Video Management

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen
Bis zu 5.000	17
Mediasite	1
OpenCast	11
Panopto	2
Vimp	3
5.001 bis 15.000	17
Lecture2Go	1
movingimage24	1
OpenCast	6
Panopto	5
Ubcast Mediaserver	1
Vimp	3
15.001 bis 30.000	9
Medial	1
Mediasite	1
OpenCast	3
Panopto	3
Vimp	1
Mehr als 30.000	8
FlowCasts	1
Medial	1
OpenCast	5
Ubcast Mediaserver	1
Gesamtergebnis	51

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
Duale Hochschule	1
Ubcast Mediaserver	1
Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	26
Lecture2Go	1
Mediasite	1
movingimage24	1
OpenCast	13
Panopto	6
Ubcast Mediaserver	1
Vimp	3
Universität	24
FlowCasts	1
Medial	2
Mediasite	1
OpenCast	12
Panopto	4
Vimp	4
Gesamtergebnis	51

Knowledge Management

The mentions are:

The satisfaction ratings are distributed as follows

A satisfaction score of 1 stands for "very dissatisfied" and 10 for "very satisfied".

The license types are distributed as follows:

The following types are mentioned as operating models:

The following table shows the solutions used grouped by facility size:

Anzahl Studierende	Nennungen	
Bis zu 5.000		12
Confluence		2
dokuwiki		2
Mediawiki		2
Microsoft SharePoint		4
Wiki		2
5.001 bis 15.000		20
Alfresco Share		1
Confluence		7
dokuwiki		1
Fosswiki		1
Mediawiki		2
Microsoft SharePoint		6
TRAC		1
Twiki		1
15.001 bis 30.000		9
Confluence		5
dokuwiki		1
Mediawiki		2
Microsoft SharePoint		1
Mehr als 30.000		8
Confluence		2
dokuwiki		1
Mediawiki		3
Microsoft SharePoint		1
Twiki		1
Gesamtergebnis		49

The following chart groups the deployed solutions by university type:

Hochschultyp	Nennungen
▣ Duale Hochschule	1
Microsoft SharePoint	1
▣ Forschungseinrichtung	1
Mediawiki	1
▣ Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften	23
Alfresco Share	1
Confluence	8
dokuwiki	2
Fosswiki	1
Mediawiki	2
Microsoft OneNote	1
Microsoft SharePoint	7
TRAC	1
▣ Sonstiges	1
Confluence	1
▣ Staatlich anerkannte private Hochschule	1
Microsoft SharePoint	1
▣ Universität	23
Confluence	7
dokuwiki	3
Mediawiki	6
Microsoft SharePoint	3
Twiki	2
Wiki	2
Gesamtergebnis	50

List of questions

General Questions: Please provide us with some basic information. (All information is optional)

- From which type of university or research institution do you come? (University, University of Applied Sciences, University of Art / Music, Church university, Dual university, State-recognized private university, Research institution)
- In which state is your facility located? (List of federal states)
- How many students does your university have? (Up to 5,000, 5,001 to 15,000, 15,001 to 30,000, More than 30,000)

Questions for each software category:

- Which solution do you use? (Free text)
- Is the system commercial, open source, self-developed or hybrid? (Commercial, Open Source, Self-developed, Hybrid)
- How do you operate the system? Internally, externally or mixed? (Operation on own servers on site by us, operation on own servers on site by a service provider, operation outside the university by us, operation outside the university by a service provider, operation partly by us, partly by a service provider).
- How satisfied are you with the solution? (Please select on a scale of 1 - 10, where 1 indicates low satisfaction and 10 indicates very high satisfaction).
- What comments do you have? (Free text)

Groups of questions about the software categories:

- Campus Management: Examples are HIS GX, HISinOne, CampusNet, CampusOnline, SAP SLCM)
- Backup software: examples are Spectrum Protect, Bacula, NetBackup
- CMS (Content Management System): Examples are Typo 3 or Wordpress
- Chat / instant messenger solution: examples are Mattermost, Rocketchat, Slack or Matrix

- DMS (Document Management System): Examples are d.3, ELO, OpenText,
- FIS (Research Information System): Examples are Pure (Elsevier), Converis (Clarivate Analytics), Symplectic Elements (Symplectic/Digital Science), HIS or FactScience (QLEO).

- Calendar: Examples are Exchange, Open Xchange, SOGo
- LMS (Learning Management System): examples are Moodle, Ilias, Stud.IP, Canvas
- Mail: Examples include Exchange, Open Xchange, Dovecot
- Private cloud / VM management: Examples are VMWare, OpenStack, Proxmox
- Project management: Examples are OpenProject, Gitlab, JIRA
- RM (Resource Management): Examples are SAP, HIS, Mach
- Sync-n-Share: Examples are Dropbox, OwnCloud, NextCloud, Seafile
- Ticket / Incident Management System: Examples are OTRS, Zammad, JIRA
- Video management: Examples are Panopto, OpenCast, Mediasite
- Video conferencing: Examples are Zoom, BBB, WebEx, Jitsi
- Knowledge management: Examples are Confluence, Mediawiki, Sharepoint, Twiki